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NATURAL POLYMERS & NOVEL APPLICATIONS

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ABSTRACT

The two primary constituents in any pharmaceutical formulation are the active ingredient and the excipients. Excipient is made up of numerous ingredients that are essential to the production of dosage forms. Polymers are used as an excipient in any dosage form. Drug release can be influenced by polymers, which should also be suitable, stable, non-toxic, and cost-effective. Three major categories can be used to classify them: natural, semi-synthetic, and synthetic polymers. In oral drug administration systems, polymers are commonly employed as excipients for rate-controlling, taste-masking, protecting, and stabilizing purposes. These days, producers are more likely to use natural polymers because of the numerous issues with drug release and the negative consequences of synthetic polymers. Polysaccharides, which are natural polymers, are biocompatible and asymptomatic. This review discusses various natural polymers, their advantages over synthetic polymer & novel applications in pharmacy.

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INTRODUCTION

The term "polymer" refers to an arbitrary quantity of monomer units. Sometimes a compound is referred to be a high polymer when it contains an extremely high number of monomers. Monomers with the same molecular weight and structure or chemical makeup are not the only kind of monomers that can form polymers^[1]. Every molecule is made up of an enormous number of individual structural components connected by covalent bonds in a predictable way. Polymerization is the process by which monomers join together to generate polymers^[2]. Three types of polymers are available: semi-synthetic, synthetic, and natural polymers. The primary source of synthetic polymers is petroleum oil, which is created by humans. They are used in many commercial sectors as well as in pharmaceutical applications, and they are mostly produced by addition and condensation polymerization & are used in pharmacological applications as well as a variety of commercial industries. Natural resources include plants, algae, animals, microorganisms, and so on from which natural polymers are extracted or derived. Different natural polymers are slightly modified to create semi-synthetic polymers. In the pharmaceutical industry, natural polymers have a few significant benefits over synthetic polymers^[3]. Natural polymers are extremely useful in pharmaceutical formulations because they can be used to make viscous liquid formulations, inhalable and injectable systems, films, beads, and micro particles^[2]. The use of natural polymers as excipients in the pharmaceutical industry is growing daily. The primary factors that set them apart from other sources are their low cost, availability, safety concerns, and biodegradability. Natural sources come in a great variety of forms and attributes. Thus, they are universally applicable in pharmaceuticals^[4].

History:

Polymer potential is one of the great ideas of the 20th century. It was developed in the 1920s amid postponed discussions, and its validation is inextricably linked to the name of H. Staudinger, the 1953 Nobel Prize winner^[5]. Natural polymers were used to make some of the first polymers that humans created, such as the cellulose nitrate used to make cinema films. Later, cellulose acetate is a safer and less explosive material replaced this film. Furthermore, cinema cameras still use acetate film today. The synthetic fibers of rayon, which you may find in some of your clothes, are likewise made from cellulose. During shortages, such as the Second World War, when there wasn't enough silk or rubber to go around because we were at war with the countries that supplied them, natural polymers also had an impact on synthetic polymers. Thus, methods for creating synthetic rubber and nylon, two examples of related natural products, were developed. Novel techniques like cross linking were developed to enhance naturally occurring polymers. Rubber that has been cross linked becomes stronger and resists melting in hot weather^[6].

Advantages of natural polymers over synthetic polymers:

Biodegradable:

Naturally occurring polymers are produced by all living organisms. They show no adverse effects on the environment or human beings. In contrast, synthetic polymers, being prepared with the help of chemicals, have side effects on the atmosphere as well as on human beings.

Biocompatible and non-toxic:

Chemically, nearly all of these plant materials are carbohydrates in nature and composed of repeating monosaccharide units. Hence, they are non-toxic as compared to synthetic polymers.

Economic:

Natural polymers are cheaper due to their production cost.

Safe and devoid of side effects:

They are found in a natural form and hence, safe and have no side effects whereas synthetic polymers being prepared by using chemicals have side effects.

Easy availability:

Natural polymers are growing in the form of herbs in many counties being economical than synthetic polymers and having no side effect and keeping in view their huge application in many industries, they are produced in large quantity hence their availability is ensured than synthetic Polymers^[2].

Classification of natural polymers

In general terms, natural polymers can be classified into polysaccharides, proteins and nucleic acids.

Polysaccharides:

They are long chains of mono saccharides joined by glycosidic bonds. Examples include Agar, Aloe vera, starch, cellulose, starch, guar gum, karaya gum etc. from plant origin. Chitin, psyllium, alginates, xanthan gum etc... From animal origin

Proteins:

They are made up of amino acids joined by peptide bonds. They fulfill structural, enzymatic and transport functions in organisms. Examples include wheat gluten, soy protein,

Nucleic acids:

They are polymers of nucleotides that store and transmit genetic information. The best-known examples are DNA and RNA.

The classification of natural polymers is based on their chemical composition, structure and biological functions. Understanding the diversity of these polymers is essential to appreciate their importance in biology and industrial applications^[7].

Natural polysaccharides

O-glycosidic bonds bind monosaccharide (sugars) together to form polysaccharides. Variations in the composition of monosaccharide. These polysaccharides have distinct sets of physicochemical properties depending on the makeup of their monomers and their biological source. Since polysaccharides are formed from renewable resources such as microbes, plants, and animals, they are found in a wide variety of natural settings. Most polysaccharides oxidize at temperatures over their melting point and are soluble in water^[8]. Natural polysaccharides are recognized as safe for targeting delivery due to their superior characteristics, including non-toxicity and non-reactivity, easy availability on a large scale, relative cheapness, significant biocompatibility and extraordinary biodegradability^[9].

Aloevera

One type of aloe, a member of the xanthorrhoeaceae family, is known by the common name aloevera^[10]. There are seventy-five potentially active ingredients in aloe vera, including vitamins, enzymes, minerals, carbohydrates, lignin, saponins, amino acids, and salicylic acids. Vitamins: It has antioxidant vitamins A (beta-carotene), C, and E. Choline, folic acid, and vitamin B12 are also present in it^[11]. Sub-Saharan Africa, the Arabian Peninsula, and some Indian Ocean islands are home to them in large numbers^[12].

Applications

- Aloe vera has a broad spectrum of antibacterial activity, both for inhibiting gram-positive and negative bacteria.
- The gel of the plant has been processed for medicinal and cosmetic application, such as wound healing, anti-inflammatory^[13].

Agar

Agar, also known as agar-agar, is made of dried gelatinous material derived from *Gelidiummamsii* (Gelidaceae), as well as from several other red algae species, including *Pterocladia* and *Gracilaria* (Gracilariaceae).

Applications

- Agar is utilized as a laxative, bacterial culture medium, pill disintegrants, surgical lubricant, emulsifying agent, gelling agent in suppositories, and suspending agent.
- used in the making of jelly, confections, tissue culture research, and microbiological investigations^[2].
- use as an emulsifying agent, stabilizing agent, suppository base, suspending agent, sustained-release agent, tablet binder, thickening agent and viscosity-increasing agent^[14].

Starches

The primary reserved carbohydrate element in green plants is starch, which is mostly contained in seeds and subterranean organs. Granules, or starch grains, are the form in which starch is found. Many starches, such as those found in potatoes (*Solanum tuberosum*), rice (*Oryza sativa*), wheat (*Triticum aestivum*), and maize (*Zea mays*), are approved for use in medicinal products^[15]. A carbohydrate known as starch, or amyllum, is made up of many glucose units bonded together by glycosidic bonds^[16].

Applications

- Thermoplastic starch is used in packaging, containers, mulch films, textile sizing agents, adhesives^[2].
- starch as a pharmaceutical excipient is as binder and disintegrate in the formulation of tablets and other solid dosage forms^[17].

Karaya gum

Gum karaya or gum sterculia, also known as Indian gum tragacanth, is a vegetable gum produced as an exudate by trees of the genus *Sterculia*. Chemically, gum karaya is an acid polysaccharide composed of the sugars galactose, rhamnose and galacturonic acid.

Applications

- It is used as a thickener and emulsifier in foods, as a laxative, and as adhesive.
- Delivery of essential oils in patches^{[18],[19]}.

Chitin

The most prevalent organic component in the skeletons of invertebrates is chitin, a polysaccharide derivative with acetyl and amino groups. It is mostly present in arthropods, annelids, and mollusks. It is also a component of many fungi's mycelia and spores.

Applications

- Chitosan and their derivatives (N-trimethylchitosan, mono-N-carboxy methyl Chitosan) are safe and effective absorption enhancers to improve mucosal, nasal, peroral drug delivery of hydrophilic macromolecules such as peptide and protein drugs and heparins.
- Chitosan nanoparticles and micro particles are also suitable for controlled drug release^[2].

Psyllium

Psyllium mucilage is obtained from the seed coat of Plantago ovata by milling the outer layer of the seeds.

Applications

- Psyllium husk was combined with various excipients, such as hydroxyl propyl methylcellulose, to create a new gastro-retentive drug delivery method for ofloxacin that is swellable and bio adhesive^[20].

Natural proteins

A naturally occurring polyamide is typically a protein. This polymer is made up of an amide group that is found in the human body's backbone chain. Collagen is a naturally occurring polymer that is classified as a protein. It is the component of connective tissue found in human skin.

Collagen

Collagen is the primary protein component of animal connective tissues. The most abundant sources of collagen are pig skin, bovine hide, and pork and cattle bones. 27 types of collagens exist and composed of different polypeptides, which contain mostly glycine, proline, hydroxyproline and lysine. The flexibility of collagen chain depends only on the glycine content^[21].

Applications

- Collagen films are used in ophthalmology as drug delivery systems for slow release of incorporated drugs.
- It was also used for tissue engineering including skin replacement, bone substitutes, and artificial blood vessels and valves^[21].

Soy protein

There are three types of soy proteins: textured soy protein, soy protein concentrate, and soy protein isolate, depending on the production process. The most refined form of soy protein is soy protein isolate, which has a protein content of almost 90%. In essence, soy protein concentrate is soybeans stripped of their water-soluble carbohydrates. It has almost 70% protein in it.

Applications

- It has been used since 1959 as an ingredient in a variety of foods for its functional properties, which include emulsification and texturizing.
- soy protein has been increasing, mainly because of its health benefits. It has been proven that soy protein can help prevent heart problems^[2].

Nucleic acids

Biological macromolecules known as nucleic acids are polymers of nucleotide repeating monomers. A sugar molecule, a phosphate group, and a nitrogenous base make up a single nucleotide. A nucleoside is made up of just one sugar molecule and a nitrogenous base. These are substantial biomolecules that are necessary for all viruses and cells to function. Genomic information is expressed and stored by nucleic acids, which is one of their primary roles. The information required by cells to produce proteins is encoded in DNA, RNA^[22].

DNA&RNA

The two forms of nucleic acids -deoxyribonucleic acid (DNA) and ribonucleic acid (RNA)—are naturally occurring polymers present in living things. DNA is a double-stranded molecule that houses the genetic information needed for all known living things as well as many viruses to develop, function, grow, and reproduce. Single-stranded molecules called RNA are involved in many biological activities, such as the creation of proteins, the control of genes, and the transfer of genetic information^[23].

Applications

- Nucleic acid-based drug delivery systems: can be made more selective and effective by functionalizing them with ligands or antibodies that target cell surface receptors or biomarkers.
- Polymer-Drug Conjugates: offer regulated drug release profiles by releasing therapeutic agent in response to stimuli, such as variations in pH, temperature, or enzyme activity.
- Gene delivery vehicles: these may be engineered to target tissues or organs and present therapeutic opportunities for cancer, genetic abnormalities, and other illnesses^[22].

CONCLUSION

The use of polymers in medicine delivery systems is essential. The use of new polymers has advantages but also has the potential to be harmful due to their toxicity and other negative characteristics. Therefore, we can conclude that natural polymers can be a good replacement for synthetic polymers and that employing natural polymers can help mitigate many of the negative consequences of synthetic polymers. The use of natural polymers (like aloe vera, karayagum, Psyllium, DNA& RNA etc... Listed) can be recommended for future research.

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Abbreviations:

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